

masking agent. Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ag^{1+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} could be masked with 10% potassium cyanide solution, while Cd was precipitated as HDPTA complex after adding chloral hydrate as a demasking agent for the Cd-cyano complex. Cadmium was determined from a solution containing Fe^{3+} and Pb^{2+} by prior precipitation of the diverse ions with HDPTA at pH 4.0. Cadmium could be determined in presence of Sn^{2+} when the latter was first oxidized to Sn^{4+} and then masked with ammonium oxalate. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—INFLUENCE OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM (Cd^{2+} taken = 6.86 mg)

Foreign ion (mg added)	Error (mg)	Foreign ion (mg added)	Error (mg)
Ag^{1+} (50)	+ .004	Fe^{3+} (80)	+ .003
Pb^{2+} (65)	+ .004	Sb^{3+} (70)	- .002
Zn^{2+} (75)	+ .001	Bi^{3+} (60)	+ .003
Hg^{2+} (80)	+ .002	AsO_4^{3-} (60)	+ .001
Cu^{2+} (93)	- .001	Sn^{2+} (90)	+ .004
Mn^{2+} (65)	- .003	F^- (80)	+ .002
Co^{2+} (60)	+ .001	CH_3COO^- (>100)	+ .002
Ni^{2+} (90)	+ .002	Tartrate	+ .003
		Oxalate	- .002
Al^{3+} (70)	- .001	Citrate	+ .003

Precision and Accuracy : The relative mean error and the relative standard deviation were found to be 0.24% and 0.32% respectively.

References

1. H. R. FLÖCK, *Analyst*, 1937, **62**, 378.
2. A. K. MAZUMDAR, *Analyst*, 1939, **64**, 874.
3. H. FUNK, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1942, **123**, 241.
4. W. D. NORDLING, *Chemist Analyst*, 1956, **45**, 44.
5. C. MAHR, *Mikrochim. Acta.*, 1938, **3**, 300.
6. S. C. SHOME, *Current Science*, 1944, **13**, 257.
7. N. C. SOGANI and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 81.
8. S. C. SHOME, H. R. DAS and B. DAS, *Anal. Chem*, 1966, **38**, 1522.

A Simple Batch Dilatometer for Measurement of Excess Volumes

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A simple batch dilatometer for direct measurements of excess volumes of binary organic mixtures is described in figure 1. Limb A ends in a ground glass disc D with a pin hole in the centre and can be sealed with a ground teflon disc D' overlapped by metal disc D'' and clamp E. Limb B carries a calibrated capillary P at its top to register the volume change. The two components are taken in the two limbs separated by mercury M contained in connecting tube L. Volume of the component in limb B can

Fig. 1. A simple batch dilatometer

be adjusted by requisite amount of mercury contained in it. Two such dilatometers with bulb capacities around 2.5, 2.5 and 0.5, 4.5 cm^3 have been used to study the excess volumes of cyclohexane(1)+benzene for entire composition range. Requisite amount of pure, double distilled and thoroughly degassed mercury was placed in the connecting tube L and then 5-7 times, frozen degassed and melted samples were filled by means of hypodermic syringes carrying stainless steel needles, first one in limb A followed by sealing, weighing and then second in limb B. Purities of the liquids used were checked by determining their densities and refractive indices which agreed with the literature values very well. Temperature of the thermostat was controlled to $25 \pm .005^\circ$. The capillary P was calibrated at each centimetre point and volume change for an observed change in levels, was determined graphically. The $V_m^E(x)$ values observed for various compositions $x\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12} + (1-x)\text{C}_6\text{H}_6$ have been fitted to the following equation,

$$V_m^E = x(1-x)2.5887 - 0.1195(1-2x) + 0.0044(1-2x)^2 \dots (1)$$

The observed values of V_m^E along with their deviations (δV_m^E) from the corresponding calculated values from equation (1) are given in Table 1. Observed values have a root mean square deviation of $0.0013 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which is of the order of

NOTES

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXCESS VOLUMES V_m^E FOR $xC_6H_{12} + (1-x)C_6H_6$ AT 2.98.15K AND THEIR DEVIATIONS δV_m^E FROM EQUATION 1.

x	V_m^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$10^4 \delta V_m^E$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	x	V_m^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$10^4 \delta V_m^E$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
0.0603*	0.1425	16	0.5190	0.6488	14
0.0879	0.1991	-8	0.5604	0.6414	1
0.1089	0.2421	-1	0.5713	0.6364	-18
0.1319*	0.2847	-19	0.6141	0.6207	7
0.1613	0.3384	-11	0.6698*	0.5825	9
0.2576	0.4838	-4	0.6856	0.5659	-18
0.3874	0.6088	8	0.8033	0.4204	-3
0.4691	0.6424	-5	0.8761	0.2923	13
0.4749	0.6468	28	0.9051*	0.2301	-8

* See Text.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF MOLAR EXCESS VOLUMES OF $xC_6H_{12} + (1-x)C_6H_6$ DETERMINED WITH DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES AND FITTED IN $V_m^E/cm^3 mol^{-1} = x(1-x)A + B(1-2x) + C(1-2x)^2$

	a	b	c	d	e	f	g
0.1	0.2246	0.2297	0.2294	0.2297	0.2276	0.2318	0.2249
0.2	0.4030	0.4092	0.4092	0.4104	0.4049	0.4130	0.4058
0.3	0.5337	0.5390	0.5393	0.5418	0.5347	0.5458	0.5494
0.4	0.6160	0.6193	0.6197	0.6237	0.6116	0.6241	0.6230
0.5	0.6472	0.6496	0.6497	0.6551	0.6313	0.6535	0.6546
0.6	0.6271	0.6289	0.6284	0.6349	0.6207	0.6313	0.6325
0.7	0.5538	0.5558	0.5545	0.5615	0.5487	0.5563	0.5560
0.8	0.4259	0.4283	0.4264	0.4328	0.4231	0.4273	0.4248
0.9	0.2418	0.2440	0.2424	0.2465	0.2413	0.2426	0.2391

	A	B	C	
a This work	Batch dilatometric	2.5887	-0.1195	0.0044
b Kumaran and McGlashan ¹	Dilution dilatometric	2.5983	-0.0990	0.0518
c Stokes, Levien and Marsh ²	—do—	2.5988	-0.0901	-0.08445
d Goates, Ott and Moellmer ³	Vibrating densitometric	2.6206	-0.1168	0.0395
e Radojkovic', Tasic' and Djordjevic' ⁴	Densitometric	2.565	-0.095	0.063
f Weeks and Benson ⁵	Magnetic float	2.6141	-0.0744	0.0337
g Wood and Austin ⁶	Pyknometric	2.6180	-0.0986	-0.0633

uncertainties in the experimental determinations. (0.0011 for the temperature variation of $\pm 0.005^\circ$ and .0002 cm³ mol⁻¹ for uncertainties in the composition). V_m^E values at rounded mole fractions have been compared in Table 2 with the reported values determined by different techniques. To test the reproducibility of the results, four mole fractions marked with asterisk were studied by making fresh lot of solvents. The agreement is satisfactory. Comparison of our results with those obtained using non-dilatometric techniques reveals that no systematic conclusion or reason regarding the deviations may be drawn. Vibrating densitometer³ gives higher values for all mole fractions while a similar instrument⁴ gives lesser values for most of the range of compositions. Values determined by magnetic float are the highest of all the techniques. Our simple dilatometer which does not involve the use of any standard joint gives quite satisfactory results agreeing to the dilution dilatometric technique values.

References

1. M. K. KUMARAN and M. L. MCGLASHAN, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1977, 9, 259.
2. R. H. STOKES, B. J. LEVIEN and K. N. MARSCH, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1970, 2, 43.

3. J. R. GOATES, J. B. OTT and J. F. MOELLMER, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1977, 9, 249.
4. N. RADOJKOVIĆ, A. TASIĆ, B. DJORDJEVIĆ and D. GROZDANIĆ, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1976, 8, 1111.
5. I. A. WEEKS and G. C. BENSON, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1973, 5, 107.
6. S. E. WOOD and A. E. AUSTIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 480.

Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Rubus moluccanus* Linn. (*Rosaceae*)

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RUBUS moluccanus Linn. (*Rosaceae*) is a plant of tropical India and grows abundantly in South India. The leaves and fruits of the plant are used as a remedy for the nocturnal micturation of children¹.

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